

COOPERATIVE LEARNING IN INCLUSIVE SETTINGS IN PRIMARY MATHEMATICS – CONNECTING TASK DESIGN AND STUDENTS’ SOLUTION STRATEGIES

Nina Flottmann

Bielefeld University, Institute for Didactics of Mathematics, Germany

As a primary teacher I find myself in an area of conflict between the heterogeneity of the primary students – irrespective of their specific intellectual, physical and social-emotional capacities, the design of tasks and learning environments and the aim to allow for cooperative learning, which plays an important role for motivation, development of social skills and social integration in school. Hence, the design-based research project that forms the basis of this paper seeks to investigate cooperative learning processes in inclusive classroom settings. Two crucial aspects of the study are the task design and the monitoring and documentation of children’s solution strategies in cooperative settings.

INTRODUCTION

Following Feuser’s (1998) paradigm with respect to ‘joint learning on a shared topic’ for inclusive education, teachers in Germany and other countries all over the world are presented with the challenge to develop learning environments and tasks that address students with a wide range of abilities and promote (mathematics) learning for all with and from each other. However, the implementation of this paradigm into practice, i.e. to include and to accept all the specific intellectual, physical, social as well as emotional capacities of students and their individual as well as collective mathematics learning processes, appears to be a special problem in mathematics classrooms, as research of teacher knowledge and beliefs by Korff (2015) suggests.

In order to overcome this theory-practice dilemma, teachers need to develop and install learning trajectories based on task design as well as children’s solution strategies which are proven to foster mathematics learning in order to understand and connect individual learning with patterns of cooperation. Furthermore, teachers need to be able to

- assess where students stand in their mathematical development and understanding,
- know their students’ special needs and
- scaffold and support their individual and collective learning.

To be able to do all of this in their classrooms, teachers need a good understanding of what constitutes a suitable task for individual and collective mathematics learning in inclusive settings as well as information about what solution strategies students might develop and execute and how an appropriate scaffolding can help them to overcome hurdles and difficulties they encounter along the way.

In this context, the design-based research project that forms the basis of this paper seeks to investigate cooperative learning processes in small group work. A crucial aspect of the study is the task design. Fermi problems have been found suitable for cooperative learning in mixed-ability groups (e.g. Peter-Koop, 2004). Hence, the following section will provide an overview of the literature on cooperative problem solving and modelling and identify requirements with respect to the study’s task design. Furthermore, the methodological approach that guided the design of the study – design-based research – and its adaptation to the specific research interest will be explained. Finally, first results from a pilot study with third- and fourth-graders will be presented.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Fermi Problems in Cooperative Group Work

The curriculum for mathematics teaching and learning in German primary schools has got different topics; one of them is “measurement” (Ministerium für Schule und Weiterentwicklung des Landes NRW, 2008). The pupils develop sustainable fundamentals and knowledge skills to handle with different measurement (e.g. length, weight, time, money). One main goal is the acquisition of competences in modelling for skills that are needed in everyday life (Peter-Koop, 2003, p. 113). Modelling means complex and realistic problem solving with developing a mathematical model (Maaß, 2011). In access to international competitive studies different mathematical tasks are designed, which are challenging, meaningful, allow different strategies and solutions, proceeding competences (like modeling) and includes all facets of pupils’ abilities (Walther, Granzer, & Köller, 2008).

The idea of Fermi problems goes back to the Physician and Noble prize winner Enrico Fermi (1901-1954), who developed tasks for his students, which implicate several approaches with different answers and solutions (e.g. “How many piano tuner live in Chicago?”). These problems have a high degree of complexity and can only be solved by giving a reasonable estimate. Peter-Koop (2004) investigated primary children’s mathematical modelling of Fermi problems. Furthermore, Fermi problems such as *How many cars will be caught in a 3 km traffic jam on the motorway?* share the characteristic that the initial response of the problem solver is that the problem could not possibly be solved without recourse to further reference material. However, while individuals frequently reject these problems as too difficult, Clarke and McDonough (1989) pointed out that “pupils, working in cooperative groups, come to see that the knowledge and processes to solve the problem already reside within the group” (p. 22).

The analysis of the classroom-based data (Peter-Koop, 2004) indicated that Fermi problems can be solved in sensible and appropriate ways by third and fourth graders in mixed ability groups and even in groups with typically rather low achieving children. While in traditional problem solving at primary school level only one modelling cycle is needed, Fermi problems can serve as “model-eliciting tasks” (Lesh & Doerr, 2000, p. 380), because the required modelling process extends beyond the application of a standard algorithm and necessitates multiple modelling cycles with multiple ways of thinking about givens, goals and solution paths (Bell, 1993). Lesh and Doerr (2000) point out that model development is learning. Hence, the outcome of the modelling activity can be a conceptual tool that exceeds the solution of a specific problem. The results of the study by Peter-Koop agrees with the findings from the analyses of secondary students’ modelling processes by Lesh and Doerr (2000) who highlighted “the need for teachers to examine students’ developing models in order to assess student knowledge and understanding and to foster continued model development in ways that evolve as the student models evolve” (p. 375).

The curriculum for mathematics teaching and learning in German primary schools requires that teachers initiate and foster cooperative learning among their students (Ministerium für Schule und Weiterentwicklung des Landes NRW, 2008, p.14). The social integration and the cooperative learning of being involved with all individuals’ abilities is one of demands. Pupils should be lead to argue, accept other perspectives, deal with other vies and express their own thoughts and strategies (Ministerium für Schule und Weiterentwicklung des Landes NRW, 2008, p.10 ff). Teachers can best accommodate this requirement by developing cooperative settings in which communication and cooperation are also the motor for individual learning. Johnson and Johnson (1999) have established core elements for cooperative teamwork, i.e. positive interdependence, individuality, accountability, social skills, face-to-face interaction

and group processing. Based on their initial work following publications introduce a wide scope of teaching strategies that aim to initiate and foster cooperative learning (e.g. Green & Green, 2005; Johnson, Johnson, & Holubec, 2005). However, these strategies rather address teacher-initiated group work.

In contrast to these approaches, in her doctoral dissertation Röhr (1995) advocates and investigates student cooperative group work that results from the mathematical tasks themselves and is not initiated ‘on top’ of a task by the teacher or the textbook. She argues that cooperative skills can best develop when the need to cooperate with others is not initiated or requested by the teacher but rather comes from within the problem solving task that requires the students to jointly look into the ask, to discuss possible strategies, to argue for specific approaches and to jointly develop a solution as their cooperation has a shared goal (ibid, p. 75). Cooperative group should be explored by a significant Fermi problem, which leads by discussion and exploration to a solution.

However, typically not all of the students choose to participate in these joint activities. Engaging these children in cooperative group discussions presents a special challenge for teachers. It is therefore a particular research interest of this project to analyze how primary students cooperatively solve Fermi problems that relate to their real-world experiences as well as to their mathematical competencies with respect to their mathematical learning processes and the arising cooperative patterns of interaction.

The methodological approach chosen with respect to this specific research interest is design-based research as it allows to include and connect the design of the specific tasks to be used in the classroom-based study with empirical insights into the occurring learning processes (e.g. Prediger, 2018).

Design-based Research

The fundamental intention of design-based research in education as described by Bakker (2018) is also known under various other related terms characterizing similar approaches: *educational design research* (Plomp & Nieveen, 2013; van den Akker, Gravemeijer, McKenney, & Nieveen, 2006), *design experiments* (Brown, 1992; Cobb, Confrey, diSessa, Lehrer, & Schauble, 2003), *design science* (Collins, 1990; Wittmann, 1995) or *didactical design research* (Prediger, 2018) to name the most prominent terms. All these approaches have a common goal, that is to investigate a problem arising from and identified through classroom practice. In a first step the identified problem is related to theory. Following is the development, implementation and analysis of an intervention resulting in the characterization and analysis of the design and develop it for re-design. Plomp and Nieveen (2013) describe this approach as “*the systematic analysis, design and evaluation of educational interventions with the dual aim of generating research-based solutions for complex problems in educational practice, and advancing our knowledge about the characteristics of these interventions and the processes of designing and developing them*” (p. 18).

Prediger (2018, p. 33) highlights two main aims of design research: (1) to develop learning arrangements for supporting classroom practice, and (2) to gain insights in mathematical arrangements for didactical theory formation. In order to reach these aims and to classify for design-based research, according to Bakker (2018, p. 18) five significant characteristics have to be fulfilled: (1) Development of theories about learning and how to support learning, (2) Interventionist nature of the research, (3) Prospective and reflective components, (4) Invention and revision in order to form an iterative process, and (5) Transferability. Plomp & Nieveen (2013, p. 17) provide the following illustration of the research process and its design cycles:

Figure 1: Iterations of systematic design cycles (Plomp & Nieveen, 2013, p.17)

METHODOLOGY

Investigating Cooperative Group Work through Design-based Research

Transferring the theory of design-based research to the empirical study described in this paper the main *problem* can be summarized as the tension between the demand for providing inclusive mathematics education and the need to support and foster all students irrespective of their individual capacities and special needs. The special focus is solving Fermi problems in cooperative group work. The *design and development of a prototype* is the investigation of a mathematical learning environment (Fermi problems) to be *evaluated* and optimized for students and teachers. The following figure based on the original illustration by Plomp and Nieveen (2013) (see Fig. 1) depicts this cyclic process and identifies the main characteristics of this project in the process of design-based research.

Figure 2: Adapted cyclical process

With respect to cooperative learning another research setting aims at the optimization of the learning environment. The challenge is to move beyond cooperative learning as a kind of ‘social decoration’ to cooperative group work that is predominantly inherent in the mathematical task. In this view the key question is how to support and scaffold students in their cooperative learning without restricting their mathematical thinking and understanding. The assignments must be designed that cooperative learning is useful and necessary.

Research Questions

The following research questions guide this design-based research project:

- How can mathematical learning environments be developed that promote and encourage students with a wide range of abilities?
- Which strategies do students demonstrate and use to solve a Fermi problem? What kind of support is helpful and/or needed?
- Which processes are mappable in cooperative group work? What constitutes mathematical learning environments that are suitable for inclusive settings?

Another aspect that erases from the analysis is the crucial role the teacher plays, which must be focused as well (Henningsen & Stein, 1997; Leiss, 2007).

Data Collection and Analysis

For the data collection of the pilot study small groups of up to five children from inclusive Grade 3 and Grade 4 mathematics classrooms have been videotaped while solving a Fermi problem. The selection of the groups was determined by parental consent. During the first round the groups were determined by the home group teacher who favored ability grouping. In the second round the mathematics teacher was responsible for the grouping and chose mixed-ability groups. Data from the third round was collected at the university math lab which is visited by classes from the local primary schools after prior registration. Since neither the children nor their potential special needs were known to the lab staff, here the groups were chosen arbitrarily. This heterogeneity of the groups is important for researching if cooperative learning that is task based is possible, useful and meaningful. The video recordings of the groups were transcribed following explicit and previously determined transcription rules. In addition, the course of the group work was recorded in the form of episode plans (i.e. a protocol of the chronological sequence of the main steps followed by the group). Children's solution strategies were analyzed based on a multi-cyclic model of the modelling process (as described by Peter-Koop (2004)). Further analyses will include the use of MaxQDA on the written transcripts in order to investigate and describe the cooperative processes displayed during the group work.

FIRST RESULTS OF THE PILOT STUDY

In order to relate problems from the students' real-world experiences (e.g. see Maaß, 2004, p.14ff) and their classroom experience, three settings have been chosen as starting points for further mathematical investigations:

Setting 1: Towards the end of the school year a Grade 4 class was planning a church service focussing the symbol "door" and had worked on the topic interdisciplinary from a variety of perspectives in several school subjects. The students started to think about, how often they themselves went through different doors within the school building and the question arose: "How many times in the past four school years have the students of our class been going through our classroom door?"

Setting 2: All the Grade 3 students of a local primary school had to attend a bicycle training and pass a test to be allowed to come to school by bike. As in the years before, on the days of the training, there were bicycles parked all over the school yard. This lead to the following question: "If all the bicycles of the third graders are lined up – one behind the other – how long would that 'chain of bicycles' be?"

Setting 3: The Fermi problem that the groups who visited the university lab school encountered, is related to a specific feature of the university building and its various elevators – a feature that provides a certain degree of fascination for the visiting students. Hence, they could easily relate to the question: "How many children can simultaneously ride in all the elevators of the main building?"

Initial analyses of the video transcripts and episode plans indicate that the approaches taken by the different groups vary substantially. Each group chose a different starting point for the modelling activities and subsequently followed different strategies. Some of the groups quickly developed an expedient approach, while it took other groups much longer to agree on a solution strategy.

As an example is shown an episode plan in figure 3 and one part of the modelling cycle of a third grade group dealing with the task of setting 2 - “bicycle chain” in figure 4

time	phase / abstract
start till #00:02:02-2#	introduction / task:
#00:02:02-3# till #00:06:27-0#	argumentation and processing I: finding a representative; agreement: 1,60 m as a representative for 1 bicycle
#00:06:27-1# till #00:12:08-2#	argumentation and processing II: group calculates length of bicycles in a bicycle chain for one class
#00:12:08-4# till #00:12:24-6#	introduction / reminding the task
#00:12:24-7# till #00:14:57-6#	processing III: group calculates length of bicycles for the next third grade
#00:14:57-7# till #00:15:32-7#	agreement: How many classes belong to the third graders?
#00:15:32-8# till #00:16:17-6#	processing IV: group calculates length of bicycles for the next third grade
#00:16:17-6# till #00:17:06-9#	processing V: group calculates length of bicycles for the next third grade
#00:17:07-0# till #00:18:38-9#	processing VI: group calculates length of bicycles for the next third grade
#00:18:39-0# till #00:23:40-1#	processing and calculation: total length of a bicycle chain of all bicycles of the third graders

Figure 3: episode plan / task “bicycle chain” / group D

The detailed transcribed episode will be shown during the conference.

Further analyses of the videos as well as the transcripts show that all groups have worked intensively and productively. They could identify with the respective task and work together cooperatively. Only few children chose to work subsidiary or co-existent (Wocken, 1998). Further stages of the project will focus on these children and the optimization of the task design in this respect.

Another focus of analysis will be the different grouping strategies – ability grouping, mixed-ability grouping and random grouping. With only one exception, all groups worked productively and naturally together.

During the conference presentation more detailed results from the different groups will be introduced and discussed, including excerpts from the group discussions, the episode plans and the respective modelling cycles.

Figure 4: modelling cycle / task “bicycle chain” / group D

REFERENCES

- Brown, A. L. (1992). Design Experiments: Theoretical and methodological challenges in creating complex interventions in classroom settings. *The Journal of the Learning Sciences*, 2(2), 141–172.
- Clarke, D. J., & McDonough, A. (1989). The problems of the problem solving classroom. *Australian Mathematics Teacher*, 45(2), 20–24.
- Cobb, P., Confrey, J., diSessa, A., Lehrer, L., & Schauble, L. (2003). Design experiments in educational research. *Educational researcher*, 32(1), 9–13.
- Collins, A. (1990). *Toward a Design Science of Education: Technical report No.1*. New York: Center for Technology in Education.
- Feuser, G. (1998). Gemeinsames Lernen am Gemeinsamen Gegenstand: Didaktisches Fundamentum einer allgemeinen (integrativen) Pädagogik. In A. Hildeschiedt & I. Schnell (Eds.), *Integrationspädagogik. Auf dem Weg zu einer Schule für alle* (pp. 19–35). Weinheim: Juventa.
- Green, N., & Green, K. (2005). *Kooperatives Lernen im Klassenraum und Kollegium: Das Trainingsbuch*. Seelze: Kallmeyer.

- Henningsen, M., & Stein, M. K. (1997). Mathematical Tasks and Student Cognition: Classroom-Based Factors That Support and Inhibit High-Level Mathematical Thinking and Reasoning. *Journal for Research in Mathematics Education*, 28(5), 524–549.
- Johnson, D. W., Johnson, R., & Holubec, E. (2005). *Kooperatives Lernen, kooperative Schule: Tipps - Praxishilfen - Konzepte*. Mülheim: Verlag an der Ruhr.
- Johnson, D. W., & Johnson, R. (1999). *Learning together and alone: Cooperative, competitive and individualistic learning*. Boston: Allyn & Bacon.
- Korff, N. (2015). *Inklusiver Mathematikunterricht in der Grundschule: Erfahrungen, Perspektiven und Herausforderungen* (1. Aufl.). *Basiswissen Grundschule: Vol. 31*. Baltmannsweiler: Schneider Hohengehren.
- Leiss, D. (2007). "Hilf mir, es selbst zu tun": Lehrerinterventionen beim mathematischen Modellieren. *Texte zur mathematischen Forschung und Lehre: Vol. 57*. Hildesheim, Berlin: Franzbecker.
- Lesh, R., & Doerr, H. (2000). Symbolizing, communicatin and mathematizing: Key components of models and modeling. In P. Cobb, E. Yackel, & K. McClain (Eds.), *Symbolizing and communicating in mathematics classrooms* (pp. 361–383). Mahwah, New York: Erlbaum.
- Maaß, K. (2004). *Mathematisches Modellieren im Unterricht: Ergebnisse einer empirischen Studie*. *Texte zur mathematischen Forschung und Lehre: Vol. 30*. Hildesheim: Franzbecker.
- Maaß, K. (2011). *Mathematisches Modellieren in der Grundschule*. Kiel: IPN Leibniz-Institut f. d. Pädagogik d. Naturwissenschaften an d. Universität Kiel.
- Ministerium für Schule und Weiterbildung des Landes NRW (2008). *Richtlinien und Lehrpläne für die Grundschule in Nordrhein-Westfalen*. Frechen: Ritterbach.
- Peter-Koop, A. (2003). "Wie viele Autos stehen in einem 3-km-Stau?" - Modellbildungsprozesse beim Bearbeiten von Fermi-Problemen in Kleingruppen. In S. Ruwisch & A. Peter-Koop (Eds.), *Gute Aufgaben im Mathematikunterricht der Grundschule* (pp. 111–130). Offenburg: Mildenerger.
- Peter-Koop, A. (2004). Fermi problems in primary mathematics classroom: Pupils' interactive modelling process. In I. Putt, R. Faragher, & M. McLean (Eds.), *Mathematics education for the third millenium: towards 2010. Proceeding of the 27th annual conference of the Mathematics Education Research Group of Australia, Townsville* (pp. 454–461). Sydney: MERGA.
- Plomp, T., & Nieveen, N. (2013). *Educational Deign Research*. Enschede: SLO.
- Prediger, S. (2018). Design-Research als fachdidaktisches Forschungsformat. In Fachgruppe für Didaktik der Mathematik der Universität Paderborn (Ed.), *Beiträge zum Mathematikunterricht* (pp. 33–40). Münster: WTM.
- Röhr, M. (1995). *Kooperatives Lernen im Mathematikunterricht der Primarstufe*. Wiesbaden: Deutscher Universitätsverlag.
- van den Akker, J., Gravemeijer, K., McKenney, S., & Nieveen, N. (2006). *Educational design research*. London: Routledge.
- Walther, G., Granzer, D., & Köller, O. (Eds.) (2008). *Lehrer-Bücherei: Grundschule. Bildungsstandards für die Grundschule: Mathematik konkret* (7. Auflage). Berlin: Cornelsen.
- Wittmann, E. C. (1995). Mathematics Education as a 'design science'. *Educational Studies in Mathematics*, 29(4), 355–374.
- Wocken, H. (1998). Gemeinsame Lernsituationen: Eine Skizze zur Theorie des gemeinsamen Unterrichts. In A. Hildeschmidt & I. Schnell (Eds.), *Integrationspädagogik. Auf dem Weg zu einer Schule für alle* (pp. 37–52). Weinheim: Juventa.